

FIRST INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

ELMINA **2018**

PROGRAM

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Rectorate of the University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia
August 27-29, 2018
<http://elmina.tmf.bg.ac.rs>

Organized by:
Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts and Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy,
University of Belgrade

Endorsed by:
European Microscopy Society and Federation of European Materials Societies

FIRST INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ELMINA 2018
Program and Book of Abstracts

Publisher: Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts
Knez Mihailova 35, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia
Phone: +381 11 2027200
<https://www.sanu.ac.rs/en/>

Editor: Velimir R. Radmilović and Vuk V. Radmilović

Technical Editor: Vuk V. Radmilović

Cover page: Vuk V. Radmilović

Printed in: Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts
Knez Mihailova 35, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia
Phone: +381 11 2027128
stamparija@sanu.ac.rs

Circulation: 50 copies

ISBN 978-86-7025-785-6

Metformin and Itraconazole Combination is Effective Against Fibrosarcoma in Hamsters

Kosta J. Popović¹, Dušica J. Popović², Dušan Lalošević²,
Dejan Miljković², Ivan Čapo², Jovan K. Popović³

¹ Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad,
Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

² Department of Histology and Embryology, Faculty of Medicine,
University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

³ Department of Pharmacology, Toxicology and Clinical Pharmacology,
Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

We have carried out small-scale research on anticancer effects of metformin and itraconazole combination. Possibilities of synergistic anticancer metformin-itraconazole interactions and multitargeting safe therapy, based on the previous separate preclinical investigations, are the main reasons for antitumor testing of their combination on our experimental fibrosarcoma model in hamsters. Our aim was to give modest contribution to accelerated development of effective, safe and a low-cost adjuvant anticancer treatment with nontoxic drugs that are already registered for other indications.

Metformin exhibited anticancer effects *in vitro* in number of various cancer cell lines. The anticancer effects of metformin were explained by different mechanisms [1, 2]. In our previous experiment, we found anticancer effects of metformin on BHK-21/C13 fibrosarcoma in hamsters [3]. In diabetic patients, metformin is usually comedicated with the most common and safest antimicrobial agent itraconazole, since fungal infections are frequent in diabetes. This combination is nontoxic in humans. Itraconazole, like metformin, possesses anticancer properties. Multiple common or diverse mechanisms of anticancer action of metformin [3] and itraconazole [4] were identified.

24 Syrian golden hamsters of both sexes, weighing approximately 100 g, were randomly allocated to 4 equally sized groups. 2×10^6 BHK-21/C13 cells in 1 ml were injected subcutaneously into the animals' back. The first group started peroral treatment with physiological solution, the second with metformin 500 mg/kg daily, the

third with itraconazole 250 mg/kg daily and the fourth with a combination of metformin 500 mg/kg and itraconazole 250 mg/kg daily, via a gastric probe 3 days before tumor inoculation. After 3 weeks, when the tumors were approximately 2 cm in the first group, all animals were sacrificed. The blood was collected for glucose and other analyses. The tumors were excised and weighed and their diameters were measured (Figure 1). The tumor samples were pathohistologically (HE) and immunohistochemically (Ki-67, CD 31, COX IV, GLUT-1, iNOS) assessed (Figure 2) and the main organs toxicologically analyzed. Tumor volume was determined using the formula $L \times S^2 / 2$, where L was the longest and S the shortest diameter. Ki-67-positive cells in the tumor samples were quantified. Images were taken and processed by software UTHSCSA Image Tools for Windows Version 3.00. Statistical significances were determined by the Student's *t*-test.

Peroral treatment with a metformin and itraconazole combination significantly inhibited fibrosarcoma growth in hamsters without toxicity. This was verified by significantly decreased tumor weight and volume and by reduced proliferation status of tumor cells, shown by Ki-67 staining on hamster tumor sections. Pathohistological and immunohistochemical evaluation revealed a decrease in tissue penetration, an expansion of necrosis and hemorrhagic areas and a reduction of vasculature in all analyzed slices of tumors (Figure 2) treated with the combination of metformin and itraconazole, when compared with control group.

Our results led us to conclude that administration of metformin in combination with itraconazole may be candidate for an effective and safe nontoxic anticancer adjuvant and relapse prevention treatment [5].

References:

- [1] X Sui *et al*, *Mol Pharm* **12** (2015), 3783.
- [2] B Dirat *et al*, *Mol Cancer Ther* **14** (2015), 586.
- [3] DJ Popović *et al*, *Eur Rev Med Pharmacol Sci* **21** (2017), 5499.
- [4] H Tsubamoto *et al*, *Oncol Lett* **14** (2017), 1240.
- [5] The authors acknowledge funding from the Republic of Serbia, Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Provincial Secretariat for High Education and Scientific Research, Grant No. 142-451- 2469/2017 (JP) and Republic of Serbia, Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development, Grants No. 171039 (JS) and 172013 (DM).

Figure 1. a) BHK fibrosarcoma in hamster; b) mitoses.

Figure 2. BHK fibrosarcoma: a) tumour angiogenesis; b) lymphoplasmacytic inflammatory cell infiltration and tumour necrosis.